

CIMMYT Global Wheat Program – 2022 Target Product Profiles for Global Wheat Improvement

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Background

During 2022, definition of target market segments for CIMMYT wheat breeding has supported definition of target product profiles for spring, durum and winter wheat. This is based on the Excellence in Breeding Toolbox for “product design and management”. The consolidated information across OneCGIAR crops is available here: <https://excellenceinbreeding.org/toolbox/tools/cgiar-seed-product-market-segment-database> which also describes the methodology used. Here we provide a summary of and links to the 2022 CIMMYT wheat product profiles for winter, spring, and durum wheat.

Winter wheat

Breeding pipelines

Two breeding pipelines have been defined for CIMMYT winter wheat: (1) *Hard winter, cold tolerant & irrigated, normal maturity* (denoted HWW-CTI-NM) and (2) *Hard winter, cold tolerant, drought tolerant, normal maturity* (denoted HWW-CTD-NM). These two pipelines target market segments in Central Asia, West Asia and North Africa as summarized in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Two breeding pipelines are defined for CIMMYT winter wheat breeding, targeting market segments in Central and West Asia and North Africa.

Target product profiles

Product profiles are defined according to grain and processing traits, nutritional enhancement, agronomic and disease traits. For winter wheat, no specific production, multiplication, or unique product registration traits apply so these fields in the product profiles are marked as not applicable (NA). Traits are listed by category and assigned a measurement scale which is used in selection along with a minimum score. The traits are differentiated by requirement: either as “must have” or “nice to have” as well as the requirement for improvement (vs. maintenance). Indication of a trait as a threshold trait indicates it is a requirement for release of material from the breeding pipeline.

The **(1) HWW-CTI-NM breeding pipeline** delivers to two product profiles in Central Asia, West Asia and North Africa. The first targets 2,080,000 hectares in West Asia (Afghanistan, Iran, Turkey) and the second targets 1,370,000 hectares in Central Asia (Georgia, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan).

The **(2) HWW-CDT-NM breeding pipeline** delivers to three product profiles in Central Asia, West Asia and North Africa. The first targets 7,400,000 hectares in West Asia (Afghanistan, Iran, Turkey, Syria), the second targets 450,000 hectares in North Africa (Algeria, Morocco) and the third targets 2,800,000 hectares in Central Asia, West Asia, and North Africa (Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Georgia, Armenia, Turkmenistan).

The full descriptions of the *five* product profiles delivered from the *two* winter wheat breeding pipelines can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433325>

Spring wheat

Breeding pipelines

Five breeding pipelines have been defined for CIMMYT spring wheat: (1) *Hard white, optimum environment*; (2) *Hard white, heat tolerant, early maturity*; (3) *Hard white, drought tolerant, normal maturity*; (4) *Hard white, drought tolerant, early maturity* and (5) *Hard white/red, high rainfall*. These five pipelines target eight global market segments in Latin America and the Caribbean, East Africa, Central Asia, West Asia and North Africa and South Asia as summarized in **Figure 2**. An additional potential new market segment has also been defined in Kazakhstan and will be further developed.

Target product profiles

As for winter wheat, spring wheat product profiles are defined according to grain and processing traits, nutritional enhancement, agronomic and disease traits. No specific production, multiplication, or unique product registration traits apply at this time, so these fields in the product profiles are marked as not applicable (NA). Traits are listed by category and assigned a measurement scale which is used in selection along with a minimum score. The traits are differentiated by requirement: either as “essential” or “nice to have” as well as the requirement for improvement (vs. maintenance). Indication of a trait as a threshold trait indicates it is a requirement for release of material from the breeding pipeline. In contrast to winter wheat, a current breeding pipeline can deliver to more than one global market segment (as summarized in Figure 2) meaning that multiple (different) product profiles are defined. Product profiles are defined within breeding pipelines and for different One CGIAR regions.

Figure 2. Five breeding pipelines are defined for CIMMYT spring wheat breeding, targeting eight global market segments in Latin America and the Caribbean, East Africa, Central Asia, West Asia and North Africa and South Asia.

Targeted market segment
 Largest market segment in the group or market segments
 all very similar in size
 Spillover market segment
 Future market segment

The **(1) Hard white-optimum environment breeding pipeline** delivers to two global market segments (hard white, optimum environment, normal maturity; and hard white, optimum environment, heat tolerant, normal maturity) denoted as HW-OE-NM and HW-HT-NM, respectively. This pipeline delivers five product profiles across South Asia, North Africa, West Asia, Latin America, and East Africa. The first (HW-OE-NM_South Asia) targets 20,790,000 hectares in South Asia (India, Pakistan, Nepal), the second (HW-OE-NM_North Africa) targets 1,260,000 hectares in North Africa (Egypt, Morocco), the third (HW-OE-NM_West Asia) targets 1,430,000 hectares in West Asia (Afghanistan, Iran, Turkey), the fourth (HW-OE-NM_Latin America) targets 150,000 hectares in Latin America (Mexico) and the fifth (HW-OE-HT-NM_Sub-Saharan Africa) targets 410,000 hectares in East Africa (Ethiopia, Nigeria and Sudan). Additional spillover countries are defined for each of the product profiles in different regions.

The **(2) Hard white, heat tolerant, early maturity breeding pipeline** delivers to one global market segment (hard white, heat tolerant, early maturity denoted as HW-HT-EM). This pipeline delivers two product profiles across South Asia and Latin America. The first (HW-HT-EM_South Asia) targets 10,250,000 hectares in South Asia (India, Pakistan, Nepal, Bangladesh) and the second (HW-HT-EM_Latin America) targets 150,000 hectares in Latin America (Bolivia, Mexico). Additional spillover countries are defined for each of the product profiles in different regions.

The **(3) Hard white, drought tolerant, normal maturity breeding pipeline** delivers to two global market segments (hard white, drought tolerant, normal maturity; and hard red, drought tolerant, normal maturity both currently denoted as HW-DT-NM due to the simplicity of selection for white and red grain). This pipeline delivers five product profiles across South Asia, North Africa, Central Asia, East Africa and West Asia. The first (HW-DT-NM_South Asia) targets 1,382,000 hectares in South Asia (India, Pakistan, Nepal)

and the second (HW-DT-NM_North Africa) targets 2,085,000 hectares in North Africa (Libya, Morocco, Tunisia, Algeria). The third (HW-DT-NM_Central Asia) targets 490,000 hectares in Central Asia (Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan), the fourth (HW-DT-NM_East Africa) targets 970,000 hectares in East Africa (Ethiopia) and the fifth (HW-DT-NM_West Asia) targets 1,940,000 hectares in West Asia (Afghanistan, Iran, Turkey). Additional spillover countries are defined for each of the product profiles in different regions.

The **(4) Hard white, drought tolerant, early maturity breeding pipeline** delivers to one global market segment (hard white, drought tolerant, early maturity denoted HW-DT-EM) in South Asia via a single product profile (HW-DT-EM_South Asia) which targets 7,000,000 hectares in India.

The **(5) Hard white, high rainfall and hard red, high rainfall, normal maturity breeding pipeline** delivers to two global market segments (hard white, high rainfall, normal maturity; hard red, high rainfall, normal maturity denoted collectively as HW/R-HiR-NM due to the simplicity of selection for white and red grain). This pipeline delivers six product profiles across East Africa, Western Asia, North Africa, Central Asia and Latin America. The first (HW-HiR-NM_East Africa) targets 520,000 hectares in Ethiopia. The second (HR-HiR-NM_East Africa) targets 243,000 in East Africa (Kenya, Tanzania) and is differentiated from the previous product profile by the preference for red grain. The third (HR/W-HiR-NM_Western Asia) targets 1,240,000 hectares in Western Asia (Iran, Turkey). The remaining three product profiles represent relatively small geographic areas with the fourth (HW-HiR-NM_North Africa) targeting 31,000 hectares in North Africa (Morocco, Tunisia), the fifth (HW-HiR-NM_Central Asia) targeting 40,000 hectares in Tajikistan and the sixth (HR-HiR-NM_Latin America) targeting 146,000 hectares in Latin America (Bolivia, Mexico). Additional spillover countries are defined for three of the product profiles in different regions.

The full descriptions of the *seventeen* product profiles delivered from *five* spring wheat breeding pipelines can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434005>.

Durum wheat

Breeding pipelines

Three breeding pipelines have been defined for CIMMYT durum wheat: (1) *Amber durum, optimum environment, normal maturity (AD-OW-NM)*; (2) *Amber durum, drought tolerant & input-responsive normal maturity (AD-DTIR-NM)* and (3) *Amber durum, heat tolerant, early maturity (AD-HT-EM)*. These three pipelines serve four market segments (and one potential new market segment) in Latin America, East Africa, Central and West Asia, North Africa and South Asia as summarized in **Figure 3**.

Target product profiles

As for winter and spring wheat, product profiles are defined according to grain and processing traits, nutritional enhancement, agronomic and disease traits. No specific production, multiplication, or unique product registration traits apply at this time, so these fields in the product profiles are marked as not applicable (NA). Traits are listed by category and assigned a measurement scale which is used in selection along with a minimum score. The traits are differentiated by requirement: either as “must have” or “nice to have” as well as the requirement for improvement (vs. maintenance). Indication of a trait as a threshold trait indicates it is a requirement for release of material from the breeding pipeline. The three current breeding pipelines deliver to four global market segment (as summarized in Figure 3). Product profiles are defined within breeding pipelines and for different One CGIAR regions.

Figure 3. Three breeding pipelines are defined for CIMMYT durum wheat breeding, targeting four global market segments in Latin America and the Caribbean, East Africa, Central Asia, West Asia and North Africa and South Asia.

The **(1) Amber durum, optimum environment, normal maturity breeding pipeline** delivers five product profiles for optimum environment and normal maturity conditions across South Asia, West Asia, Central Asia, North Africa, and Latin America. The first (AD-OE-NM_South Asia) targets 121,000 hectares in South Asia (Pakistan, Nepal), the second (AD-OE-NM_West Asia) targets 540,000 hectares in West Asia (Afghanistan, Iran, Syria, Turkey), the third (AD-OE-NM_Central Asia) targets 80,000 hectares in Azerbaijan. The fourth (AD-OE-NM_North Africa) targets 340,000 hectares in North Africa (Algeria, Egypt, Morocco) whilst the fifth (AD-OE-NM_Latin America) targets 262,000 hectares in Latin American (Chile, Mexico).

The **(2) Amber durum, drought tolerant, input-responsive normal maturity breeding pipeline** delivers four product profiles for drought tolerance combined with input responsiveness and normal maturity across East Africa, North Africa, West Asia, Latin America. The first (AD-DTIR-NM_East Africa) targets 140,000 hectares in East Africa (Eritrea, Ethiopia) and the second (AD-DTIR-NM_North Africa) targets 2,400,000 hectares in North Africa (Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia). The third (AD-DTIR-NM_West Asia) targets 1,595,000 hectares in West Asia (Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq, Syria, Turkey) and the fourth (AD-DTIR-NM_Latin America) targets 60,000 hectares in Argentina.

The **(3) Amber durum, heat tolerant, early maturity breeding pipeline** delivers a product profile in India (AD-HT-EM). This targets 570,000 hectares with a distinct product profile.

The full descriptions of the *ten* product profiles delivered from *three* durum wheat breeding pipelines can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7439208>

Summary and next steps

This document summarizes the developed of 2022 product profiles for CIMMYT wheat breeding. Input and feedback are welcome to improve the data presented and the targeting of breeding objectives. During 2023 we will work with One CGIAR Accelerated Breeding and Market Intelligence Initiatives to further refine market segmentation and target product profiles.

The full CIMMYT wheat breeding product profiles for 2022 can be found here:

- Akin, Beyhan. (2022). CIMMYT winter wheat product profiles 2022 (Version V1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433325>
- Govindan, Velu, Crespo Herrera, Leonardo, Singh, Ravi, Huerta, Julio, & Bhavani, Sridhar. (2022). CIMMYT spring wheat product profiles 2022 (Version V1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434005>
- Ammar, Karim. (2022). CIMMYT durum wheat product profiles 2022 (Version V2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7439208>